

OPEN ACCESS

EDITED BY
Maria Elisa Magri,
Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil

REVIEWED BY
Sekato Maremane,
University of the Free State, South Africa
Samkele Mnyango,
Department of Water and Sanitation,
South Africa

*CORRESPONDENCE
Erika Cristina Francisco,
✉ erika.francisco@slu.se

RECEIVED 02 March 2026
REVISED 27 March 2026
ACCEPTED 30 March 2026
PUBLISHED 29 April 2026

CITATION
Francisco EC, Ignácio PSdA and
McConville JR (2026) A system dynamics
model integrating urine diversion and
resource recovery for sustainable
wastewater management.
Front. Environ. Sci. 14:1821368.
doi: 10.3389/fenvs.2026.1821368

COPYRIGHT
© 2026 Francisco, Ignácio and
McConville. This is an open-access article
distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).
The use, distribution or reproduction in
other forums is permitted, provided the
original author(s) and the copyright
owner(s) are credited and that the original
publication in this journal is cited, in
accordance with accepted academic
practice. No use, distribution or
reproduction is permitted which does not
comply with these terms.

A system dynamics model integrating urine diversion and resource recovery for sustainable wastewater management

Erika Cristina Francisco^{1*}, Paulo Sergio de Arruda Ignácio² and Jennifer Rae McConville¹

¹Department of Energy and Technology, Swedish University of Agricultural Science/SLU, Uppsala, Sweden, ²School of Applied Sciences, University of Campinas/Unicamp, Limeira, São Paulo, Brazil

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in tourism-driven and climate-sensitive coastal regions experience pronounced seasonal hydraulic variability that challenge conventional performance assessment frameworks. The objective of this study is to apply system dynamics modeling to guide strategic decision-making in the adoption of urine diversion (UD) systems for increased nutrient recovery. Specifically, the study evaluates the environmental performance and strategic implications of integrating UD into centralized wastewater management under conditions of seasonal population variability and hydraulic stress. Using the case of Gotland, Sweden, and the Visby wastewater treatment plant, a 5-year simulation was conducted to represent tourism-driven population fluctuations. Environmental performance was assessed through nitrogen and phosphorus emissions, marine eutrophication potential (MEP), water footprint (WF), carbon footprint (CF), and avoided freshwater abstraction to reflect freshwater scarcity conditions. Six scenarios were analyzed, including three conventional treatment configurations under baseline and hydraulic stress conditions and three scenarios with progressively increased UD adoption. Simulation results revealed recurrent summer peaks in nitrogen (0.030 kg m^{-3}) and phosphorus (0.0018 kg m^{-3}) discharges under conventional configurations (S1) despite compliance with annual average thresholds. Progressive implementation of UD significantly reduced peak nutrient emissions across environmental indicators. Capture and treatment of urine enabled nutrient recovery which could be used as a locally available fertilizer that can off-set dependency on imported mineral fertilizers. Additionally, avoided water abstraction with higher levels of UD highlighted freshwater conservation benefits in water-limited contexts. Integrating urine diversion as a decentralized nutrient recovery strategy can enhance system resilience, reduce environmental impacts, and support circular sanitation objectives within centralized wastewater management systems.

KEYWORDS

carbon footprint, eutrophication, fertilizer, nutrient recovery, urine diversion, wastewater, water footprint

1 Introduction

There are multiples challenges facing managers of wastewater treatment facilities. While wastewater treatment was originally designed to remove dissolved organic matter and pathogens, the focus was increasingly placed on the removal of nutrients as the impacts of eutrophication became apparent (Preisner et al., 2021). Wide-scale implementation of

treatment processes for phosphorous and nitrogen removal was rolled out in the 1990s (Zhang et al., 2022). However, many of these treatment plants are now reaching design capacity, even as regulations for removal of nutrients keep getting stricter (e.g., revised European Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive–EU UWWTD, 2024); and will soon need to undertake costly expansions and upgrading (Vatten, 2023). Even with these efforts to reduce eutrophication, the world is operating well outside the planetary boundary set for biogeochemical flows of nitrogen and phosphorus (Richardson et al., 2023). Indeed, eutrophication remains a major problem in the Baltic Sea with over 90% of the region below good environmental status (HELCOM, 2023a). At the same time, geopolitical instabilities are increasing the risk for fertilizer shortages (Vos et al., 2025) and nations are increasingly looking for ways to guarantee local fertilizer markets for food security through recycling of nutrient-rich waste flows, like wastewater. Notably, wastewater treatment plants represent the largest non-agricultural anthropogenic source of nitrous oxide (N_2O), accounting for approximately 3%–7% of total emissions. Furthermore, primarily associated with nitrogen removal processes, may contribute to more than 80% of greenhouse gas emissions from treatment processes (Song et al., 2024).

There is increasing interest in the wastewater sector for resource recovery technologies as viable solutions to the global challenges of nutrient pollution, fertilizer shortage and overloaded wastewater treatment plants. One such approach is the diversion and separate treatment of urine, which contains 9–11 g N L⁻¹, 0.3–0.7 g P L⁻¹, and around 1.5 g K L⁻¹ in human excreta (Saliu et al., 2024; Xiang et al., 2024). However, urine composition varies depending on factors such as diet, health status, and storage conditions (Martin et al., 2022; Rumeau et al., 2023). As the most nutrient-rich fraction of wastewater, separation of urine can divert large quantities of nutrients from the wastewater treatment plant, potentially extending the life of the treatment plant (Rauch et al., 2003), avoiding nutrient pollution and creating a valuable fertilizer (Martin et al., 2022). Multiple life-cycle assessment studies of urine diversion systems show that these systems result in reductions to eutrophication potentials and greenhouse gas emissions (Aliahmad et al., 2025; Appiah-twum et al., 2025; Hilton et al., 2021; Martin et al., 2022). However, large implementation of urine diversion systems remains low due to structural barriers in regulatory and institutional frameworks (Aliahmad et al., 2023). Strategic pilot projects have the potential to overcome some of these barriers by increasing knowledge and legitimacy of these options in a process of strategic niche management (Raven, 2010).

One such strategic pilot is the P2Green project being funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program. P2Green aims at fostering a transition from currently linear approaches of the water-agri-food system towards innovative nutrient recovery solutions from different sanitation systems (<https://p2green.eu/about/>). The Swedish pilot region of the P2Green project is on the island of Gotland in the Baltic Sea. Gotland is a popular summer destination which results in heavy seasonal loading at the wastewater treatment plant and seasonal water shortages. The pilot solution being tested is to collect urine from toilets and urinals during summer public events and treat it in a urine reclamation process to produce bio-fertilizer in pellet form.

The project will assess the potential benefits of this system and foster dialogue among regional stakeholders that can support the development of new governance solutions for circular nutrient flows.

As part of the P2Green project (2024), a pilot-scale nutrient recovery system was implemented on Gotland, to demonstrate a circular sanitation service chain by Sanitation 360 (<https://sanitation360.se/>), a company based in Gotland, where source-separated urine was collected from toilets and urinals deployed at public events. Stabilizing additives were used to retain nutrients and control odor during collection. The urine then underwent a proprietary drying process to concentrate nutrients, producing a solid bio-fertilizer with an NPK ratio of 15-2-4. This dry fertilizer was pelletized using binding agents to ensure compatibility with conventional agricultural equipment. The resulting pellets were applied in local barley cultivation, and the harvested barley was subsequently used by a partner brewery for beer production, thereby closing the nutrient loop.

While this pilot operates at a local scale, it provides a tangible demonstration of the broader potential of urine diversion systems to recover nutrients and reintegrate them into agricultural value chains. In a national context such as Sweden (≈ 10 million inhabitants), assuming an average urine production of 1.42 L person⁻¹ day⁻¹ (Rose et al., 2015), this corresponds to a theoretical recovery potential of approximately 46,000–57,000 tonnes of N, 1,500–3,600 tonnes of P, and around 7,800 tonnes of K per year, based on typical urine concentrations (Saliu et al., 2024; Xiang et al., 2024). These quantities are significant when compared to national agricultural fertilizer demand, indicating that urine-derived nutrients could substitute a meaningful share of synthetic fertilizers. At the municipal scale, a town of 100,000 inhabitants would generate approximately 142 m³ of urine per day, containing roughly 1.3–1.6 tonnes of N, 43–100 kg of P, and about 210 kg of K daily. Such scaling illustrates how decentralized systems, like the Gotland pilot, can contribute to a substantial nutrient recovery when implemented more broadly. These estimates highlight that source separation and treatment of urine is not only conceptually attractive but also quantitatively substantial, supporting its potential role in closing nutrient cycles, reducing dependence on mineral fertilizers, and mitigating nutrient discharges to aquatic environments.

To identify strategic interventions for upscaling urine diversion systems, we need tools to facilitate dialogue around potential options and test scenarios and business-models. Here there are limitations with life-cycle assessments which do not allow for seasonal variations or the dynamics of changing populations. Nor do they include economic, social or functional impacts of these complex systems. System dynamics, and in particular the causal loop diagrams that form the basis of the method, has been suggested as a tool for visualizing consequences of decision-making in complex systems (Guest et al., 2010). Qualitative causal loop diagrams are useful in participatory processes for identifying and discussing potential interconnections and interests of stakeholders. System interactions can then be quantified in system dynamic models (SDM) which visualize effects of population growth, infrastructure change, resource flows, and economic factors (Mohammadifardi et al., 2019; Prouty et al., 2020). SDM are useful as simulation tools for capturing the dynamics of complex

systems as input to decision-making processes. The models can highlight potential trade-offs between environmental, economic and social benefits of alternative scenarios, thus guiding strategic choices.

This study aims to propose guidelines for strategic decision-making regarding the development of urinary diversion systems (UD) by applying system dynamics modeling to better understand cause-and-effect relationships. Specifically, to evaluate the environmental performance and strategic implications of integrating UD into centralized wastewater management under conditions of seasonal population variability and hydraulic stress. Using the pilot case of Gotland, Sweden, and the Visby wastewater treatment plant as a case study, the model simulates the dynamic interactions between wastewater loading, treatment performance, and source-separated urine recovery over time. The model is applied to simulate the seasonal fluctuations of nutrient emissions from wastewater treatment, fertilizer recovery potential, carbon and water footprints. Different strategic scenarios with varying levels of urine diversion and treatment capacity at the wastewater treatment plant are applied to answer the following questions: 1) How seasonality affects the environmental impacts and how can they be mitigated? 2) How much conventional fertilizer can be substituted with urine-based fertilizer? 3) How much water can be saved using urine diversion systems?

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Case of study

The Baltic Sea, located in Northern Europe, is one of the most eutrophic marine systems globally, primarily due to excessive inputs of nitrogen and phosphorus from anthropogenic sources such as agriculture and wastewater discharges. As a semi-enclosed and brackish water body with limited water exchange, it is particularly vulnerable to nutrient accumulation, which has led to widespread hypoxia, anoxia, and long-term degradation of ecosystem functioning. Recent assessments confirm that eutrophication remains a major and persistent problem, with no clear signs of recovery during the period 2016–2021 (HELCOM, 2023b). Current monitoring data indicate that nutrient concentrations remain elevated in many basins, with dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN) around $5.0 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and dissolved inorganic phosphorus (DIP) between 0.49 and $0.59 \mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, while total nitrogen (TN) and total phosphorus (TP) concentrations typically range from 17–21 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$ and 0.64–0.95 $\mu\text{mol L}^{-1}$, respectively, in open sea areas (HELCOM, 2023a). In several sub-basins, nutrient levels remain above target thresholds, highlighting the continued magnitude of nutrient enrichment and the need for further reductions in external nutrient inputs.

Gotland, Sweden's largest island, lies within the Baltic Sea approximately 100 km from the mainland. Despite its relatively small permanent population of approximately 61,173 residents, the island experiences a substantial seasonal influx of visitors. In 2023, more than 2 million people travelled to Gotland (Region Gotland, 2023), with tourism peaking during the summer months. This results in pronounced seasonal fluctuations in water demand and wastewater generation, placing additional pressure on local

wastewater treatment systems and increasing the risk of nutrient discharges during peak periods.

In addition to tourism-driven pressures, land use on Gotland is dominated by agriculture, which represents a major source of nitrogen and phosphorus inputs due to fertilizer application and livestock production (Jordbruksverket, 2022; HELCOM, 2023a). Although industrial activity on the island is relatively limited, sectors such as food processing and small-scale manufacturing may also contribute to local wastewater loads (Statistics Sweden, 2023a; Statistics Sweden, 2023b). These combined anthropogenic pressures influence the composition and variability of influent wastewater, further complicating nutrient management. Given the environmentally sensitive context of the Baltic Sea and the persistent eutrophication problem, such seasonal and land-use-driven dynamics are of particular concern.

To address these challenges, the present study focuses on wastewater management practices in Visby, the island's main urban center, with particular emphasis on urine diversion as a decentralized strategy for reducing nutrient loads to the aquatic environment while enabling nutrient recovery for fertilizer production.

The data used in this study was collected from multiple sources, including information from the Sanitation 360 process to support urine diversion (UD) simulations. Data for the wastewater management analysis were obtained from environmental reports (Miljörapport, 2017–2024) of Visby's wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and supplemented by data from Jönsson et al. (2005) on typical wastewater composition and generation rates in Sweden. The permanent population of Visby is 24,951 inhabitants, and this value was used as the initial population parameter in the system dynamics model. The WWTP operates using a Moving Bed Biofilm Reactor (MBBR) system and is designed to treat wastewater with a pollution load of 4,200 kg of organic material per day, corresponding to 60,000 population equivalents (PE).

Additional data sources included national and regional databases: Statistics Sweden (Macrotrends, 2024) for population growth, Destination Gotland (Hållbarhetsredovisning, 2023) for ferry visitor statistics, and Swedavia Airports (Swedavia Statistik, 2021–2024) for air travel data. Ferry and airport statistics were incorporated into the population seasonality simulation.

2.2 Model development

A model is defined as a structured and simplified abstraction of reality, designed to balance between oversimplification - which may compromise analytical accuracy - and excessive complexity, which may render the system analytically intractable (Almeida, 2013). The development of SDM simulation models is typically carried out through a series of methodological steps that facilitate the systematic understanding and analysis of complex systems and problems (Francisco et al., 2023). These steps include: (i) problem scoping, where system boundaries, objectives, and key variables are defined; (ii) conceptual modelling, involving the construction of causal loop diagrams to represent system structure and feedback mechanisms; (iii) model development, where the conceptual model is translated into a quantitative stock-and-flow structure; (iv) model testing, including verification and validation of model structure, assumptions, and behavior; (v) simulation, in which scenarios are

executed to analyses system responses over time; and (vi) model updating, where the model is refined iteratively based on new data, insights, or stakeholder feedback.

Starting from the problem scoping phase, the conceptual modelling process began with the development of a causal loop diagram (Figure 1), designed to explore the interrelationships within the sanitation system in Visby, the main urban center of Gotland. The model was developed from first principles rather than adapted from existing frameworks, ensuring that system boundaries, variables, and feedback mechanisms were explicitly tailored to the local context. Model verification was conducted through iterative, stakeholder-informed validation and consistency checks of both system structure and behavior. While the model reflects the specific conditions of Visby, such as seasonal population fluctuations and operational characteristics of the local wastewater treatment system, its structure is inherently transferable. With appropriate adjustments to key parameters (e.g., population size and dynamics, influent composition, hydraulic loading, and treatment performance), the modelling framework can be readily implemented in other regions or wastewater treatment plants. This adaptability allows the approach to support context-sensitive assessments of urine diversion strategies across diverse settings. Overall, the model provides a robust, locally grounded yet scalable representation of sanitation dynamics, contributing novel insights into the integration of urine diversion within centralized wastewater systems.

Given the high complexity of the relationships, the causal loop diagram (CLD) was simplified to simulate the causal interactions among the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), urine diversion technology, and environmental indicators. The analysis of causal relationships between system components and indicators highlights key strategies or policies relevant to the transition toward more sustainable systems. However, it is important to note that, due to the complexity of the studied system, not all possible interactions were explored so, the model focus on technologies and indicators highlighted by “blocks”.

The WWTP-UrDiv (Wastewater Treatment Plant - Urine Diversion) model (Figure 2) was developed using STELLA software (version 3.7.3, 2023) and comprises two interconnected modules (A): the Wastewater Treatment Plant (B) and the Urine Diversion (C) system. The first module simulates the operation of the WWTP in Visby, accounting for seasonal fluctuations in wastewater generation driven by tourism. The second module represents the collection and diversion of urine, aimed at nutrient recovery for fertilizer production. The model components and corresponding input data and/or equations are detailed in Supplementary Table SA (Supplementary Material).

This modeling approach is consistent with circular economy principles, emphasizing resource recovery and the reduction of environmental impacts. To evaluate system performance, three environmental indicators were applied:

- Carbon Footprint (CF): Quantifies the total mass of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, expressed in tons of CO₂-equivalent (CO_{2eq}). This includes direct (Scope 1)

and indirect (Scopes 2 and 3) emissions and is commonly used to assess the climate change mitigation potential of processes (Ni et al., 2023)

- Marine Eutrophication Potential (MEP): Evaluates the potential environmental impact of nitrogen emissions (kg N) into marine ecosystems. These emissions can lead to algal blooms, oxygen depletion, and loss of biodiversity, particularly in sensitive coastal and marine environments (Ecoinvent database, 2024).
- Water Footprint (WF): A comprehensive indicator measuring the volume of water used (m³) throughout the process. It includes blue (surface and groundwater), green (rainwater), and grey (polluted water) components, providing a holistic perspective on water resource appropriation (Aldaya et al., 2011; Morera et al., 2016).

However, MEP was not evaluated for the urine diversion (UD) technology, as the process does not result in nitrogen discharge to the Baltic Sea. Additionally, the analysis considered “avoided water” abstraction from the system, reflecting freshwater scarcity constraints. In addition, fertilizer production was used as the primary output indicator to evaluate the system’s resource recovery potential.

During the model testing phase, a structured validation procedure was conducted to assess the internal consistency and empirical robustness of the model. Validation was performed by simulating a Baseline Scenario (S1) and systematically comparing the model outputs with observed annual data on wastewater generation and nitrogen emissions reported in the official environmental reports (Miljörapport, 2017–2024) of Visby’s WWTP. The primary objective of this validation step was to ensure that the representation of seasonal population dynamics and pollutant removal efficiencies reflected realistic operational conditions. However two important data limitations were identified.

First, the seasonal population data used to parameterize seasonal variability do not explicitly distinguish tourists from permanent residents. Instead, they represent total mobility flows between the island of Gotland and the mainland. Consequently, the seasonal population input required adjustment to better approximate the effective temporary population contributing to wastewater generation. To address this uncertainty, the seasonal population parameter was scaled by dividing the collected mobility data by a factor of three applying the annual average of wastewater production as validation.

Second, the pollutant removal efficiencies implemented in the model were derived from annual average values reported in the environmental monitoring data. These annual averages do not capture intra-annual (monthly) variability in treatment performance. To introduce a more conservative and operationally realistic representation of nitrogen removal dynamics, the annual average nitrogen removal rate was adjusted by applying a reduction factor of three.

These calibration adjustments were implemented iteratively until the simulated annual wastewater volumes and nitrogen emissions aligned with the reported empirical data within acceptable deviation ranges. This procedure enhanced the model’s capacity to reproduce observed system behavior while explicitly acknowledging data aggregation constraints and seasonal uncertainties.

2.3 Scenarios simulation and analysis

The model was run under six scenarios designed to represent plausible future conditions for wastewater loading on the treatment

plant and to evaluate the environmental implications of implementing urine diversion (UD). The scenarios reflect increasing hydraulic stress on the WWTP as well as gradual adoption of UD solutions. Each scenario was simulated for both modules over a period of 60 months (5 years).

2.3.1 Moderate overload (S1 - baseline)

S1 represents conditions where increased hydraulic loading reduces the hydraulic retention time (HRT), affecting key biological and physical processes in wastewater treatment. Since removal efficiency commonly follows a pseudo-first-order relationship with HRT, shorter retention times limit nitrification and denitrification and reduce sludge and particle removal efficiency, leading to higher effluent nitrogen and turbidity (Ejhed et al., 2018). Accordingly, a 20% reduction in pollutant removal efficiency is applied to represent moderate overload conditions.

2.3.2 Severe overload (S2)

This scenario extends the same principle as S1, assuming more pronounced hydraulic overloading and a 40% reduction in removal efficiency, consistent with the relationship between HRT and treatment performance described by (Ejhed et al., 2018).

2.3.3 Extreme overflow (S3)

S3 represents conditions driven by increased rainfall intensity and frequency linked to climate change, which can overwhelm combined sewer systems and wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs). Such extreme events cause higher volumes and frequencies of combined sewer overflows (CSOs) and stormwater flooding, resulting in the bypass or discharge of untreated wastewater to the environment (Li et al., 2023; Saikia et al., 2024). In this scenario, the WWTP is assumed to operate within its design capacity under normal conditions, applying standard pollutant removal rates (S1). However, once this capacity is exceeded, wastewater load is discharged untreated into the Baltic Sea. Historical data indicate that Gotland’s WWTP has experienced such overflow events in specific years between 2017 and 2024 (Miljörapport, 2017–2024).

2.3.4 Seasonal urine diversion (S4)

Uses the same reduced treatment efficiency as Scenario 1 while integrating 17.5% of UD during the summer tourist season (June to August), corresponding to 50% usage of public toilet infrastructure through the implementation of dry urinals.

2.3.5 Full seasonal urine diversion (S5)

S5 maintains the treatment efficiency of Scenario 1, with 35% of UD, representing the average full utilization of public toilets (dry urinals) during the summer tourist season (e.g., S4).

2.3.6 Expanded urine diversion (S6)

In this scenario consider the full adoption of UD, through the installation of vacuum systems (substitution of flush toilets), as a

decentralization system coupled to WWTP under operation's condition as Scenario 1 (Baseline).

For Scenarios 4–6, a sensitivity analysis was conducted using three technological configurations of the urine diversion system: (a) renewable-based, (b) non-renewable-based, and (c) hybrid (renewable + non-renewable). These simulations aimed to evaluate the environmental performance under different energy sources and chemical stabilization components ([Supplementary Table SA-Supplementary Material](#)).

The simulated scenarios were statistically evaluated using analysis of variance (ANOVA) at a 95% confidence level to assess the robustness, internal consistency, and explanatory power of the model outputs. ANOVA is well suited for comparing means across multiple independent scenarios and was therefore applied to all environmental indicators and fertilizer production metrics simulated for Scenarios S1–S6. The analysis was used to quantify whether observed differences among scenarios were statistically significant and attributable to structural model configurations, seasonal forcing, and adoption levels rather than random variability. In addition, regression-based performance metrics (R^2 , adjusted R^2 , F-statistics, and Significance F) were used to evaluate how strongly temporal variability in the indicators was explained by the underlying system drivers and parameterization.

All statistical analyses were conducted on outputs generated from a dynamic 5-year simulation period of the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) and urine diversion modules. This timeframe was selected to ensure robust statistical interpretation while maintaining clarity in result visualization, as population projections and associated system dynamics exhibited repetitive patterns beyond 5 years. Graphical outputs were generated using Python (JupyterLab 4.2.5) to support comparative analysis across scenarios and to illustrate the temporal behavior of key indicators.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Statistical analysis

The ANOVA results ([Supplementary Table SB-Supplementary Material](#)) not only confirm the statistical robustness of the simulation outputs but also provide important insights when interpreted in light of prior literature on wastewater system modeling and environmental performance assessment. The consistently high coefficients of determination ($R^2 \geq 0.98$) and statistically significant F-values across scenarios indicate that the variability of environmental indicators is strongly explained by structural system dynamics rather than stochastic fluctuations. This finding is consistent with previous system dynamics applications in wastewater and sustainability contexts, which demonstrate that well-calibrated models are capable of capturing dominant causal mechanisms governing environmental outcomes ([Mohammadifardi et al., 2019](#); [Prouty et al., 2020](#)). In particular, the strong explanatory power observed here reinforces the suitability of system dynamics as a decision-support tool for complex sanitation systems characterized by non-linear interactions and seasonal variability, especially under conditions of climate and demand uncertainty ([Li et al., 2023](#)).

Moreover, the high statistical significance observed across scenarios corroborates findings from life cycle assessment (LCA) and hybrid modeling studies, which emphasize that structural interventions, such as source separation or process reconfiguration, tend to produce systematic and non-random shifts in environmental performance ([Aliahmad et al., 2025](#); [Hilton et al., 2021](#)). In this study, the ANOVA results demonstrate that differences between scenarios (S1–S6) are not only statistically significant but also structurally embedded in the system configuration, particularly in relation to hydraulic loading and urine diversion adoption levels. This extends prior literature by quantitatively showing how seasonal forcing and decentralized interventions jointly influence system behavior over time, a dimension often underexplored in conventional LCA approaches, which typically rely on static representations of system performance ([Appiah-twum et al., 2025](#)).

In the WWTP module, the particularly high F-statistics observed for carbon footprint (CF) and water footprint (WF) under scenarios with hydraulic stress (S1–S5) are consistent with empirical studies showing that population-driven inflow variability is a dominant determinant of environmental performance in treatment plants ([Morera et al., 2016](#); [Varol et al., 2024](#)). Recent advances in water-energy-carbon nexus analyses further reinforce that environmental indicators in wastewater systems are highly sensitive to operational dynamics and flow variability, highlighting the importance of integrating dynamic modeling approaches into environmental assessments ([Ni et al., 2023](#)). Conversely, the reduced variability and lower standard errors observed in Scenario S6 provide quantitative evidence of the stabilizing effect of upstream nutrient separation. This finding contributes to the growing body of literature suggesting that source-separating sanitation systems can enhance operational resilience by decoupling pollutant loads from hydraulic variability and reducing dependence on centralized treatment processes ([Guest et al., 2010](#); [Lehtoranta et al., 2022](#)).

Finally, the ANOVA results for the urine diversion module, characterized by uniformly high R^2 and near-zero significance values, confirm that environmental outcomes such as carbon footprint, avoided water, and fertilizer production are systematically driven by technological configuration and adoption level. This supports previous research highlighting that the environmental performance of decentralized sanitation technologies is highly sensitive to design choices, energy inputs, and stabilization pathways ([Appiah-twum et al., 2025](#); [Martin et al., 2021](#)). By integrating statistical validation with dynamic simulation, this study advances the literature by demonstrating that the benefits of urine diversion are not only environmentally relevant but also statistically robust and structurally consistent across multiple scenarios. In doing so, it contributes to bridging the gap between dynamic systems modeling and environmental assessment frameworks, providing a more comprehensive basis for evaluating circular sanitation strategies in complex, climate-sensitive, and resource-constrained contexts.

3.2 Marine eutrophication potential (MEP)

The simulated nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions over the 5-year period ([Figures 3, 4](#)) reveal persistent and systematic

FIGURE 3
Analysis of Total Nitrogen emissions from Visby's WWTP under scenario's simulation.

FIGURE 4
Analysis of Total Phosphorus emissions from Visby's WWTP under scenario's simulation.

differences among the six modeled scenarios (S1–S6), with pronounced seasonal variability and clear regulatory implications. Across both nutrients, the emission magnitudes confirm the dominant role of hydraulic overloading and extreme inflow conditions, as well as the strong mitigating potential of urine diversion (UD) on nutrient discharge dynamics.

Under baseline conditions (S1), nitrogen emissions (Figure 3) exhibit marked and recurrent summer peaks, reaching approximately 0.030 kg m^{-3} , clearly exceeding both the current UWWTD limit (0.015 kg m^{-3}) and the proposed draft threshold (0.010 kg m^{-3}) during high-tourism months. Winter concentrations remain substantially lower, generally between 0.005 and 0.010 kg m^{-3} , with only minor fluctuations. This pronounced seasonal contrast is primarily driven by summer hydraulic stressors commonly observed in wastewater treatment systems,

including increased influent flow due to population surges, reduced hydraulic retention time (HRT), and dilution effects from infiltration and inflow. These conditions can impair biological treatment processes, particularly nitrification and denitrification, by limiting microbial contact time and reducing process stability (Bogdanova et al., 2024). In addition, variable loading rates during peak periods may further disrupt treatment efficiency (Ukkonen and Mikola, 2024). Consequently, regulatory non-compliance is strongly associated with these transient summer hydraulic stresses rather than average operational performance.

Phosphorus emissions under S1 (Figure 4) show a comparable seasonal pattern, though at lower absolute concentrations. Winter values decline to approximately 0.0004 kg m^{-3} , while summer peaks typically reach 0.0018 kg m^{-3} . These peak concentrations remain below the current UWWTD limit (0.0020 kg m^{-3}) but consistently

exceed the proposed draft threshold (0.0007 kg m^{-3}) during high-load months (EU UWWTD, 2024). The magnitude of exceedance relative to the draft standard is therefore substantial, with peak values reaching more than twice the proposed limit. This pattern confirms that, although the plant generally complies with the current phosphorus regulation, it would experience recurrent seasonal non-compliance under the stricter draft requirements. Such behavior aligns with empirical evidence indicating that conventional WWTPs in environmentally sensitive regions frequently struggle to maintain compliance during load surges, even when annual averages appear satisfactory. The annual environmental reports of the Visby WWTP case study document recurrent nutrient emission draft exceedances between 2016 and 2024 (Miljörapport, 2017–2024), further corroborating this behavior. Importantly, the nitrogen and phosphorus results confirm that seasonal exceedances are structurally embedded in the system dynamics.

Scenario S2, representing severe hydraulic overload with a 40% reduction in treatment efficiency, shows a pronounced amplification of seasonal nitrogen peaks, with maximum concentrations reaching approximately 0.033 kg m^{-3} . Exceedances of both current and proposed UWWTD thresholds become frequent and more prolonged during summer periods. This behavior reflects reduced hydraulic retention time (HRT), which compromises nitrification and denitrification processes, leading to incomplete ammonia oxidation and insufficient nitrate removal (Mu'azu et al., 2020). Outside the peak season, S2 nitrogen values remain slightly elevated compared to S1, indicating reduced overall system resilience.

Phosphorus emissions under S2 increase more visibly compared to baseline conditions. Summer peaks reach approximately 0.0023 kg m^{-3} , thereby exceeding not only the draft threshold but also the current UWWTD limit (0.0020 kg m^{-3}) (EU UWWTD, 2024). This demonstrates that hydraulic overload compromises not only biological nitrogen removal but also phosphorus polishing capacity, likely due to reduced settling efficiency and chemical precipitation performance under shortened retention times. These results further highlight the vulnerability of centralized treatment systems operating near hydraulic capacity limits and confirm that compliance assessments based solely on annual averages may mask critical short-term exceedances with high ecological relevance.

The effect becomes most pronounced in Scenario S3, which simulates extreme overflow conditions associated with increasingly intense and frequent rainfall events. In this scenario, nitrogen concentrations exhibit sharp and erratic spikes, often exceeding 0.033 kg m^{-3} and representing the highest value observed across all scenarios. Phosphorus emissions display similarly abrupt peaks, also reaching approximately 0.0023 kg m^{-3} during extreme events as S2. These peaks clearly surpass both regulatory thresholds and reflect partial or full bypass of treatment processes. Between peak events, concentrations decline rapidly to near-baseline levels (often below 0.0003 kg m^{-3}), illustrating the episodic nature of overflow-driven emissions. Such dynamics are characteristic of combined sewer overflows (CSOs), where untreated or partially treated wastewater bypasses the treatment train and is discharged directly into receiving waters. As documented by (Perry et al., 2024), CSOs act as hydraulic safety mechanisms but simultaneously release concentrated pulses of nutrients, suspended solids, organic matter, pathogens, and

micropollutants. The simulated results are consistent with observed system behavior in Baltic Sea catchments and align with historical overflow records from the Gotland WWTP between 2017 and 2024 (Miljörapport, 2017–2024), underscoring the increasing climate sensitivity of wastewater infrastructure.

Scenarios S4–S6 evaluate the implementation of urine diversion (UD) as a decentralized source-separation strategy aimed at reducing nutrient loads entering the WWTP. This approach is increasingly recognized as an effective measure for mitigating nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) emissions at the source, given that human urine contributes the majority of nutrient loads in domestic wastewater despite representing a small fraction of total volume (Larsen et al., 2013; Harder et al., 2019).

In Scenario S4, seasonal UD applied at 17.5% coverage produces a clear and systematic reduction in both nitrogen and phosphorus emissions relative to baseline scenarios (S1–S3). Peak summer nitrogen concentrations decrease to approximately 0.026 kg m^{-3} . However, exceedances of the draft nitrogen threshold persist during periods of maximum loading. Despite this, both the magnitude and amplitude of seasonal oscillations are visibly attenuated, indicating improved system stability under transient stress conditions. Phosphorus peaks in S4 are reduced to approximately $0.0011\text{--}0.0013 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, remaining below the current directive (EU UWWTD, 2024) limit but still exceeding the proposed draft threshold during peak months. These results are consistent with previous studies showing that partial urine diversion can significantly reduce nutrient loads while improving treatment resilience, although higher implementation levels are typically required to achieve full compliance (Harder et al., 2019).

Increasing seasonal UD coverage to 35% in Scenario S5 further enhances system performance. Nitrogen peaks are reduced to approximately 0.024 kg m^{-3} , and temporal concentration profiles become smoother, with reduced inter-peak variability compared to S4. This indicates an enhanced buffering capacity against hydraulic and load variability. Although summer nitrogen concentrations still exceed regulatory thresholds, both the duration and magnitude of exceedance are clearly reduced. Phosphorus emissions under S5 show substantial improvement, with peak values generally ranging between 0.0006 and 0.0008 kg m^{-3} . In most months, concentrations remain at or below the draft UWWTD threshold (0.0007 kg m^{-3}), with only minor exceedances during extreme loading periods. This represents a marked improvement relative to S1–S3 and demonstrates that moderate UD implementation can approach compliance with more stringent phosphorus standards. Such stabilization is particularly relevant in tourism-driven coastal regions, where short-term population surges impose disproportionate stress on centralized treatment systems and exacerbate episodic eutrophication risks. Similar findings have been reported in the literature, highlighting that source separation reduces peak loading and enhances the robustness of downstream biological processes (Larsen et al., 2013; Harder et al., 2019).

The most pronounced improvements are observed in Scenario S6, representing full-scale, year-round urine diversion. Under this configuration, nitrogen concentrations remain consistently low throughout the simulation period, generally between 0.001 and 0.003 kg m^{-3} , well below both the current UWWTD limit and the proposed draft threshold across all months. Compared to

FIGURE 5
Simulated results of MEP (Marine Eutrophication Potential) from Visby's WWTP under scenario's simulation.

baseline peak emissions of approximately 0.030 kg m^{-3} , this corresponds to an approximate 90% reduction in peak nitrogen concentrations. Seasonal oscillations are effectively eliminated, reflecting the combined effect of substantial influent nitrogen load reduction and improved process stability. These findings align with previous research demonstrating that complete urine separation can remove up to 80%–90% of nitrogen loads from municipal wastewater streams (Larsen et al., 2013).

Phosphorus emissions under S6 are similarly stabilized at very low levels, typically between 0.00005 and $0.00035 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ throughout the 5-year period. These concentrations remain consistently below both current and proposed UWWTD thresholds, with minimal seasonal variability. Relative to baseline peak concentrations of approximately 0.0018 kg m^{-3} , this represents an approximate 80% reduction in peak phosphorus emissions. This level of performance confirms that full urine diversion can not only ensure compliance with existing regulatory standards but also provide a robust pathway toward meeting future, more stringent phosphorus discharge limits. The strong reduction in variability further highlights the role of source separation in decoupling treatment performance from influent fluctuations, thereby increasing overall system resilience (Harder et al., 2019).

From a broader environmental perspective, the simulated reductions in peak nitrogen and phosphorus discharges are particularly relevant in the context of Baltic Sea eutrophication. HELCOM assessments for the period 2016–2021 (HELCOM, 2023a) indicate that nutrient inputs from point sources, while reduced over recent decades, remain a significant contributor to coastal eutrophication, particularly during episodic high-flow events. The updated results confirm that urine diversion substantially reduces nutrient loads precisely during those peak periods that are most ecologically damaging. Furthermore, policy analyses indicate that

the revised UWWTD (EU UWWTD, 2024) will place increasing emphasis on stricter nitrogen and phosphorus standards, climate resilience, and resource recovery. In this context, the integration of decentralized source-separation strategies into centralized systems emerges not only as an environmental mitigation measure but also as a structural adaptation strategy for climate-sensitive and tourism-dependent regions.

Figure 5 presents the simulated Marine Eutrophication Potential (MEP) for all scenarios over the 5-year period, highlighting the strong sensitivity of marine eutrophication impacts to nitrogen emissions from the wastewater treatment plant (WWTP). Across all scenarios, MEP displays pronounced seasonal dynamics, with recurring summer peaks driven by increased hydraulic loading and reduced treatment performance.

Scenario S1, representing baseline conditions, exhibits recurrent summer MEP peaks of approximately $164 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$. These peaks coincide with periods of reduced hydraulic retention time (HRT), which transiently impairs nitrification and denitrification processes. Such behavior is consistent with documented relationships between HRT reduction and decreased nitrogen removal efficiency in Nordic WWTPs, where seasonal flow variability limits biological process stability (Räike et al., 2020). Although S1 maintains relatively low MEP values during off-peak months, the repeated summer peaks indicate a persistent contribution to coastal eutrophication pressure.

Under severe overload conditions (S2), MEP peaks increase substantially, reaching approximately $220 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$, corresponding to an increase of roughly 34% relative to S1. This escalation reflects further deterioration of biological nitrogen removal under intensified hydraulic stress, where oxygen limitation and shortened contact times suppress the activity of ammonia and nitrite-oxidizing bacteria (Mu'azu et al., 2020;

Perry et al., 2024). Such conditions are well known to exacerbate nitrogen leakage from WWTPs, particularly in systems not designed for extreme seasonal or storm-driven inflow variability.

Scenario S3 produces the most extreme eutrophication potential, with repeated peaks exceeding $261 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$. This scenario represents extreme rainfall-induced inflow events that exceed treatment capacity, resulting in partial or full bypass of the biological treatment train. These dynamics are analogous to combined sewer overflows (CSOs), which discharge untreated or insufficiently treated wastewater directly into receiving waters. Numerous Baltic Sea studies have shown that such episodic discharges contribute disproportionately to marine eutrophication, despite their relatively short duration, due to the high bioavailability of nitrogen released during stormwater-driven pulses (Preisner et al., 2021; HELCOM, 2023b).

The introduction of urine diversion (UD) in Scenarios S4–S6 markedly alters these dynamics. Seasonal UD at 17.5% coverage (S4) reduces summer MEP peaks to approximately $135 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$, corresponding to a 17% reduction relative to S1. This reduction reflects the removal of a substantial fraction of nitrogen-rich urine from the influent, thereby lowering the nitrogen load entering the biological treatment processes during peak flow periods. Increasing seasonal UD adoption to 35% in Scenario S5 further enhances mitigation, lowering peak MEP values to around $111 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$, equivalent to a 32% reduction relative to S1. In addition to reduced peak magnitude, S5 exhibits noticeably dampened seasonal oscillations, indicating improved system robustness under high-load conditions. This stabilization effect underscores the capacity of source-separation strategies to buffer centralized treatment systems against episodic hydraulic stress by reducing nitrogen loads upstream of the WWTP.

The most pronounced mitigation is observed in Scenario S6, representing full-scale, year-round urine diversion. In this scenario, MEP values remain consistently low throughout the simulation period, with peaks generally below $18 \text{ kg N}_{\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$, corresponding to a 90% reduction relative to S1. The MEP profile in S6 is characterized by minimal seasonal variability, reflecting both the substantial reduction in influent nitrogen loads and the resulting stabilization of biological treatment performance. This near elimination of seasonal peaks is particularly significant in coastal systems such as the Baltic Sea, where eutrophication impacts are strongly driven by episodic nutrient pulses rather than annual mean loads.

The ecological relevance of these reductions is underscored by regional nutrient budgets. According to HELCOM (2023b), municipal wastewater accounts for approximately 15% of nitrogen and 31% of phosphorus inputs to the Baltic Sea, with point-source nitrogen loads proving more difficult to reduce than phosphorus over recent decades. Consequently, even partial reductions in WWTP nitrogen emissions can yield disproportionate benefits for marine eutrophication status, especially in semi-enclosed and nitrogen-limited coastal waters.

Recent assessments of source-separating sanitation systems further corroborate the mitigation potential observed in Scenarios S4–S6. Urine diversion systems can capture approximately 80% of household nitrogen and 50% of phosphorus before these nutrients enter mixed wastewater streams. Life cycle assessments conducted in Nordic and Baltic contexts indicate that urine diversion can reduce

marine eutrophication potential by 46%–54% in urban systems and by up to 80%–87% in rural or semi-rural settings, where nutrient reuse is more effectively integrated into local agriculture (Lehtoranta et al., 2022). These findings align closely with the simulated MEP reductions presented here and reinforce the conclusion that urine diversion directly targets the nutrient fractions most responsible for eutrophication impacts in sensitive marine basins such as the Baltic Sea.

3.3 Carbon footprint (CF)

The simulation results presented in Figure 6 illustrate the temporal evolution of the carbon footprint (CF) of Visby's wastewater treatment plant (WWTP), representing the current centralized system, across the three modeled scenarios (S1–S3), as well as the overall CF of the combined centralized and decentralized configurations (S4–S6). Similar to the MEP, carbon footprint exhibits pronounced seasonal variability, with recurrent summer peaks driven by population-related load increases and hydraulic stress during the high-tourism season. However, the relative ranking of scenarios differs from the eutrophication results, reflecting the complex interplay between biological activity, chemical consumption, energy use, and process bypassing in determining overall greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

Under Scenario S1, representing baseline operation, CF peaks reach approximately $75\text{--}80 \text{ ton CO}_{2\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$ during summer months. These elevated emissions are primarily associated with increased chemical consumption and intensified biological treatment under high loading conditions. External carbon sources (e.g., methanol), phosphorus precipitation agents, and polymer coagulants contribute substantially to indirect GHG emissions, while enhanced nitrification-denitrification activity increases direct emissions of nitrous oxide (N_2O). Recent studies indicate that chemical dosing typically accounts for 10%–15% of the total carbon footprint of WWTPs, with carbon sources and phosphorus removal chemicals representing the dominant contributors. For example, chemical use accounted for 14.2% of total emissions in a survey of 98 WWTPs in East China, while Swedish studies report that fossil carbon from chemicals contributes 12%–17% of total carbon inflows to sewer systems, with organic chemicals alone responsible for up to 83% of this fossil carbon burden (Reppas-Chrysovitsinos et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2025). Despite these seasonal peaks, the overall CF of S1 remains relatively moderate due to the plant's reliance on biogas for heating. On-site energy recovery through anaerobic digestion and combined heat and power (CHP) generation has been shown to reduce total WWTP carbon footprints by 30%–40% compared with grid-dependent systems, substantially lowering indirect emissions associated with electricity consumption (Maktabifard et al., 2019).

In Scenario S2, where hydraulic overloading reduces treatment efficiency by 40%, CF peaks decrease slightly relative to S1, reaching approximately $68\text{--}70 \text{ ton CO}_{2\text{eq}} \text{ month}^{-1}$. This counterintuitive reduction reflects a shift in the balance between direct and indirect emissions. Under severe hydraulic stress, biological conversion processes are partially suppressed, leading to lower nitrification and denitrification rates and, consequently, reduced biogenic N_2O formation. Simultaneously, chemical dosing declines because high-performance operation cannot be sustained under

FIGURE 6

Simulated results of CF (Carbon Footprint) under scenario's simulation. The CF is expressed as tons of CO₂ equivalent (CO_{2eq}), encompassing both direct and indirect greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions associated with WWTP and UD systems. Scenarios 4–6 are presented under a hybrid energy configuration "c".

overload conditions. Although transient anoxic-oxic fluctuations can, in some systems, elevate N₂O emissions, the overall collapse of biological activity under sustained overload conditions results in a net reduction of direct GHG emissions. This behavior is consistent with observations from overloaded activated sludge systems, where reduced microbial transformation rates can lower overall carbon intensity despite deteriorating effluent quality (Kuokkanen et al., 2021).

Under extreme hydraulic stress (Scenario S3), inflow volumes exceed treatment capacity, triggering hydraulic bypass and partial or full discharge of untreated wastewater. As shown in Figure 6, peak CF values in S3 fall to approximately 68–70 ton CO_{2eq} month⁻¹, which is within the same range observed in S2 and slightly lower than S1. This similarity indicates that, despite more severe hydraulic disruption, the suppression of biological treatment processes and associated reductions in nitrification-denitrification activity limit direct N₂O formation, leading to comparable carbon footprint levels under both overload conditions. This reduction arises because bypassing the biological and chemical treatment stages significantly curtails energy use and chemical consumption, including methanol, phosphorus precipitants, and sludge-conditioning polymers. While such bypass events are clearly undesirable from a nutrient and ecological standpoint, they highlight a critical trade-off, reduced carbon footprint can coincide with substantially increased environmental harm through nutrient and pathogen discharge.

The integration of urine diversion (UD) in Scenarios S4–S6 produces a systematic and progressive reduction in CF, reflecting decreased nitrogen loading, lower oxygen demand, and reduced formation of direct GHGs. Scenarios 4–6 represent the total carbon footprint of the whole system (centralized + decentralized

system) under a hybrid energy configuration (renewable + non-renewable), as was identified as the most favorable configuration in the sensitivity analysis.

The CF peaks decline in Scenario S4 to approximately 66–69 ton CO_{2eq} month⁻¹ during the summer season. This corresponds to a reduction of roughly 14% relative to S1 peak values (≈75–80 ton CO_{2eq} month⁻¹). The decrease is primarily driven by reduced N₂O emissions associated with lower nitrification loads in the centralized plant, while the decentralized component contributes comparatively modest additional emissions under the hybrid energy mix.

In Scenario S5, with 35% seasonal UD coverage, peak CF values further to approximately 56–59 ton CO_{2eq} month⁻¹, representing an overall reduction of about 26% relative to S1. The CF trajectory under S5 exhibits visibly dampened seasonal variability compared with S1–S3, indicating enhanced robustness of the treatment system under high-load conditions. Reduced nitrogen inflow stabilizes oxygen transfer requirements and limits N₂O formation during transient process disturbances, which are well recognized hotspots for GHG emissions in biological treatment systems. Importantly, because these values represent the combined centralized-decentralized configuration, the results demonstrate that the additional infrastructure required for urine collection and handling does not offset the GHG benefits obtained from reduced biological nitrogen removal.

The most substantial mitigation is achieved in Scenario S6, representing full, year-round urine diversion under the hybrid energy configuration. In this scenario, CF peaks decline to approximately 23–25 ton CO_{2 eq} month⁻¹, while off-peak values fall to roughly 3–6 ton CO_{2 eq} month⁻¹. Relative to baseline summer peaks in S1, this corresponds to a GHG's emission reduction of approximately 70%. Seasonal variability remains present due to

residual operational energy demand and background emissions from both centralized and decentralized components; however, the amplitude of seasonal peaks is drastically attenuated. The CF profile becomes substantially lower and more stable compared to S1–S3, reflecting the combined effect of removing most nitrogen-rich urine from the influent and operating the WWTP under significantly reduced biological and chemical demand. Because nitrogen loading is the principal driver of high-global-warming-potential N₂O formation, source separation directly suppresses the dominant biochemical pathways responsible for direct emissions.

These findings remain consistent with previous modeling and life cycle assessment studies reporting 20%–47% reductions in global warming potential (GWP) when urine diversion is integrated into centralized wastewater treatment systems (Aliahmad et al., 2025; Hilton et al., 2021). The larger reductions observed under full-scale implementation in S6 reflect both high nitrogen diversion rates and the optimized hybrid energy configuration identified in the sensitivity analysis. Regional benchmarking studies indicate that none of the 16 Scandinavian WWTPs evaluated by Gustavsson and Tumlin (2013) achieved carbon-neutral operation under conventional configurations. The present results suggest that while hybrid energy supply improves performance, substantial structural emission reductions are only achieved when combined with upstream nitrogen source separation. This underscores the structural challenge of meeting the net-zero or energy-neutral requirements introduced in the revised EU Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (UWWTD) and highlights urine diversion as a complementary and enabling strategy rather than a competing alternative.

Mechanistically, conventional wastewater treatment systems exhibit elevated carbon footprints largely due to N₂O emissions, which have a global warming potential nearly 300 times that of CO₂ (IPCC, 2007). Operational disturbances, nitrite accumulation, oxygen-limited zones, and fluctuating redox conditions can further intensify N₂O and CH₄ formation (Boiocchi and Bertanza, 2022; Kuokkanen et al., 2021). By diverting urine at the source, UD reduces nitrogen loads entering aeration tanks, lowers oxygen demand, and suppresses nitrifier-denitrification pathways and other microbial processes responsible for GHG formation (Boiocchi et al., 2017). When coupled with a hybrid configuration, this strategy simultaneously addresses both direct biological emissions and indirect energy-related emissions, enhancing overall decarbonization performance.

In this context, Scenario S6 demonstrates how full-scale urine diversion, implemented within an optimized hybrid configuration, can function as a viable low-carbon transition strategy for WWTPs, aligned with Sweden's circular economy objectives and the European Commission's target of a 55% reduction in GHG emissions by 2030. Beyond climate mitigation, UD simultaneously enhances nutrient recovery, improves treatment robustness, and reduces sensitivity to seasonal and climatic variability, offering a holistic and scalable pathway for decarbonizing wastewater management in climate-sensitive and tourism-driven regions such as Gotland.

Figure 7 shows the sensitivity analysis that was conducted considering three alternative stabilization configurations: renewable-based (a), non-renewable (b), and hybrid (c), for Scenarios S4–S6. The results reveal pronounced variability in CF

across the three stabilization pathways, spanning several orders of magnitude. For all scenarios, the renewable-based configuration (a) exhibits by far the highest annual carbon footprint. Under this configuration, CF values reach approximately 5,900–6,600 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹ for S4a, increase to ~11,200–12,600 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹ for S5a, and escalate dramatically to ~84,700–94,200 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹ under S6a. These values exceed those of the non-renewable and hybrid configurations by three to four orders of magnitude, fundamentally altering the climate performance of the UD system when deployed at scale.

The unexpectedly high CF associated with configuration (a) is primarily attributable to its reliance on citric acid for urine stabilization. Although citric acid is bio-based, its industrial production involves energy-intensive fermentation processes, followed by resource-demanding downstream purification steps. As a result, citric acid exhibits a disproportionately high emission factor, which dominates the life-cycle greenhouse gas profile of renewable UD configurations. This behavior is well documented in recent life cycle assessment studies, which consistently identify citric acid as the principal contributor to global warming potential in bio-based urine stabilization pathways (Aliahmad et al., 2025; Dutta et al., 2019).

From a broader systems perspective, the sensitive analysis results underscore a critical paradox: although renewable or bio-based inputs are often assumed to confer environmental benefits, they do not inherently guarantee lower greenhouse gas emissions. Global citric acid production exceeded 2.39 million tons in 2020 and is projected to reach 2.91 million tons by 2026, driven by growing demand from the food, pharmaceutical, and bioprocessing sectors (Latif et al., 2025). Despite its classification as Generally Recognized as Safe (GRAS), citric acid production remains carbon-intensive due to high energy requirements for fermentation and purification. While emerging research suggests that the use of agro-industrial waste substrates and improved fermentation efficiency could reduce future emission factors (Dutta et al., 2019; West, 2023), such improvements are not yet reflected in current industrial-scale production.

In stark contrast, the non-renewable (b) and hybrid (c) configurations yield substantially lower carbon footprints across all scenarios. For S4, CF values remain below 8 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹ for both S4b and S4c. In S5, emissions increase modestly to ~13 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹, while in S6 they reach approximately 94–102 ton CO_{2eq} yr⁻¹. The close alignment between configurations (b) and (c) indicates that the energy mix, renewable *versus* partially fossil-based, plays a secondary role in determining overall UD system CF when sulfuric acid is used as the stabilization agent. Instead, the choice of stabilization chemistry emerges as the dominant driver of climate performance.

Taken together, the sensitivity analysis clearly demonstrates that the carbon intensity of the UD system is governed primarily by the stabilization reagent rather than by the energy source alone. While configuration (a) paradoxically exhibits the highest carbon burdens, configurations (b) and (c) provide climate-efficient stabilization pathways that effectively complement the WWTP-level emission reductions achieved under Scenarios S4–S6.

In summary, the CF assessment and sensitivity analysis highlight the necessity of coordinated optimization across both infrastructures. Achieving low-carbon wastewater management in

FIGURE 7 Sensitivity analysis of CF (Carbon Footprint) from Urine Diversion (UD) technology.

FIGURE 8 Simulated results of WF (Water Footprint) from Visby's WWTP and UD under scenario's simulation.

regions such as Gotland requires not only reducing on-site WWTP emissions through nitrogen source separation, but also minimizing upstream impacts associated with urine stabilization chemistry. When appropriately configured with low-impact

mineral acids and integrated energy strategies, urine diversion offers a robust and scalable pathway toward climate-resilient, circular wastewater management systems that deliver genuine life-cycle climate benefits.

3.4 Water footprint (WF)

Figure 8 illustrates the temporal evolution of WF over the 5-year simulation period for the centralized system (S1–S3) and for the whole system with the progressive adoption of UD (S4–S6). Under the baseline scenario (S1), summer WF peaks reach approximately $1.7\text{--}1.8 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$, while low season values decline to roughly $1.0\text{--}2.0 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$. These peaks reflect the larger water volumes conveyed, treated, and discharges during high-demand tourism periods, demonstrating the strong sensitivity of centralized wastewater systems to seasonal population dynamics. As emphasized by (Morera et al., 2016), WWTPs function simultaneously as consumers of freshwater resources, through their dependence on influent flows, and as protectors of water quality, by reducing pollutant concentrations prior to discharge. Complementary evidence from Varol et al. (2024) demonstrates that treated wastewater plays a critical role in preserving downstream water quality by preventing the pollution of large volumes of freshwater that would otherwise be required for pollutant dilution. The seasonal amplitude observed in S1 confirms that even under nominal operation, centralized systems impose substantial volumetric and dilution burdens during peak inflow periods.

Scenario S2, representing moderate hydraulic overloading, exhibits higher WF peaks than S1, reaching approximately $2.6\text{--}2.8 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$ during summer months. The increase in WF despite reduced biological treatment efficiency indicates that volumetric load, rather than wastewater quality, is the dominant driver of WF magnitude under these conditions. This behavior corroborates earlier findings by Morera et al. (2016) and Shao and Chen (2013), who concluded that the WF of WWTPs is primarily governed by system-wide water management demands and pollutant dilution requirements, largely independent of short-term fluctuations in process efficiency.

The most extreme WF values are observed in Scenario S3, where peaks exceed $4.0 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$. This scenario simulates intense rainfall-driven inflow and infiltration events that exceed treatment capacity, resulting in partial or full bypass of the treatment process. Such hydraulic shocks impose a disproportionate WF burden, as the entire volumetric load must be conveyed and assimilated by receiving waters with finite dilution capacity. Similar conclusions were reached by studies, that showed that untreated or partially treated wastewater yields the highest WF (Morera et al., 2016; Varol et al., 2024). Even under bypass conditions, the WWTP must still manage and transport excess flows, reinforcing the vulnerability of centralized systems to hydrological extremes.

The introduction of urine diversion (UD) in Scenarios S4–S6 leads to a systematic reduction in WF magnitude and seasonal amplitude. In Scenario S4 (17.5% seasonal UD), summer WF peaks decline to approximately $1.7 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$, representing a reduction of roughly 15% relative to baseline conditions. Scenario S5 (35% seasonal UD) further lowers peak values to approximately $1.5 \times 10^7 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$, corresponding to reductions of approximately 25% relative to S1. In both scenarios, winter WF values also decrease modestly, indicating that partial urine diversion reduces both volumetric inflow to the centralized plant and the pollutant load requiring dilution in receiving waters.

The seasonal oscillations remain visible but are clearly attenuated compared with S1–S3.

The lowest WF values are observed in Scenario S6, representing full-scale, year-round urine diversion. Under this configuration, summer WF peaks remain consistently below $9 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$, while low season values fall to approximately $1.0 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3 \text{ month}^{-1}$. Relative to S1, this corresponds to reductions of approximately 50% in peak WF and more than 75% relative to the extreme S3 scenario. The markedly reduced seasonal amplitude under S6 demonstrates that removing flush water and decentralizing urine collection substantially lowers the volumetric burden on the centralized WWTP throughout the year. This not only alleviates hydraulic stress during peak periods but also reduces the grey WF by decreasing the dilution capacity required to assimilate nutrient loads in receiving waters.

Overall, the results highlight the dual role of WWTPs as both hydraulic receivers and critical protectors of downstream water quality. At the same time, they demonstrate that decentralized urine diversion can substantially reduce hydraulic stress, lower water use, and decrease the grey water footprint associated with nutrient discharge. Under conditions of seasonal demand and climate-driven hydrological variability, such source-separation strategies offer a structurally robust pathway to enhance the sustainability and resilience of wastewater management systems.

Figure 9 presents the annual volume of avoided potable water associated with the implementation of urine diversion (UD) technologies in Scenarios S4–S6. Unlike the centralized WWTP assessment, where the water footprint reflects blue and grey components linked to wastewater conveyance and pollutant assimilation, the indicator used here represents water savings at the source, i.e., potable water that is no longer withdrawn from the local water system due to the replacement of conventional flush toilets by dry toilets (S4–S5) and vacuum toilets (S6).

The results show a clear and consistent increase in avoided water volumes with increasing UD adoption. Under Scenario S4, representing partial seasonal implementation with dry urinals (17.5% coverage), the avoided potable water ranges from approximately 7.1×10^4 to $7.7 \times 10^4 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$ over the 5-year period. These values remain relatively stable across years, reflecting the recurring seasonal nature of tourism-driven sanitation demand and the complete elimination of flush water for the participating user fraction.

Scenario S5, which increases seasonal UD adoption to 35%, approximately doubles the avoided water volumes, reaching $\approx 1.1 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. This proportional increase confirms that water savings scale linearly with the number of users adopting dry sanitation technologies, as flush water is eliminated entirely for these connections. The limited interannual variability further suggests that avoided water is primarily governed by user coverage and seasonal population dynamics rather than by operational fluctuations in the sanitation system.

The largest water savings are observed in Scenario S6, representing full-scale implementation using vacuum toilets. In this scenario, avoided potable water volumes reach approximately $2.2 \times 10^5 \text{ m}^3 \text{ yr}^{-1}$. Although vacuum toilets still require water for flushing, their ultra-low flush volumes result in substantial net water savings compared with conventional gravity toilets. The higher avoided volumes in S6 reflect both the full adoption rate and the

FIGURE 9
Simulated results of avoided water from Urine Diversion (UD) technology under scenarios 4–6.

cumulative effect of replacing standard flush systems across the entire user base.

Interpreting these results in the context of water-scarce regions is particularly important. Unlike traditional water footprint metrics, which may increase internally within the UD subsystem due to urine handling and stabilization, the avoided water indicator captures the net benefit to local water availability. Dry toilets and urine-diverting dry toilets (UDDTs) eliminate flush water entirely, while vacuum toilets reduce flushing demand by 25%–50%, depending on user behavior and system configuration (Todt et al., 2021). Numerous studies highlight that sanitation technologies based on source separation are among the most effective measures for reducing domestic water demand in regions facing chronic or seasonal water scarcity (Mkhize et al., 2017).

These benefits are especially relevant for Gotland, where water scarcity is a long-standing and intensifying challenge. The island is characterized by shallow soil, limited groundwater storage, and a strong reliance on local aquifers that are highly sensitive to overextraction and saline intrusion. Seasonal tourism significantly amplifies summer water demand, leading to recurrent shortages and emergency water management measures. Projections indicate that total water demand on Gotland may increase by more than 40% by 2045, driven by population growth, tourism, and climate variability (Dahlqvist et al., 2019). Under such conditions, reducing potable water consumption at the source becomes a critical adaptation strategy.

From a system-wide perspective, the avoided water volumes shown in Figure 9 represent a direct reduction in pressure on Gotland's freshwater resources. By eliminating or minimizing flush-water use, UD reduces abstraction from groundwater sources, lowers the volume of wastewater requiring conveyance and treatment, and indirectly decreases energy demand associated with pumping, treatment, and potential supplementary water supplies such as desalination. Importantly, these benefits accrue precisely during peak summer months, when both water scarcity and sanitation demand are highest.

While Scenario S6 yields the largest avoided water volumes, Scenarios S4 and S5 demonstrate that even partial, seasonal

implementation of dry sanitation can deliver meaningful water savings. This is particularly relevant in contexts where full system conversion may face social, logistical, or economic constraints. Literature consistently emphasizes that the long-term performance of dry and urine-diverting sanitation systems depends on user acceptance, adequate maintenance, and institutional support (Conroy and Mancl, 2022; Mkhize et al., 2017). Nevertheless, when these conditions are met, such systems provide robust and reliable water-saving outcomes.

3.5 Fertilizer

Figure 10 presents the annual production of dry urine-based fertilizer under Scenarios S4–S6, reflecting increasing levels of urine diversion (UD) adoption on Gotland. The results demonstrate a clear and consistent adoption-dependent gradient in fertilizer output, with relatively low interannual variability within each scenario and pronounced differences between scenarios. Under Scenario S4, which represents partial seasonal UD implementation using public urine-diverting dry toilets, annual fertilizer production remains relatively stable over the 5-year period, ranging from approximately 8.7–9.7 ton yr⁻¹. Scenario S5 nearly doubles fertilizer output, yielding between 16.5 and 18.4 ton yr⁻¹. The highest production levels are observed under Scenario S6, which models full-scale UD implementation; in this case, annual fertilizer production ranges from 128.5 to 138.4 ton yr⁻¹.

These results are consistent with the well-established nutrient composition of human urine. Although urine accounts for only about 1% of domestic wastewater volume, it contains approximately 80% of household nitrogen (N) and around 50% of phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) (Vinnerås et al., 2006). Consequently, diverting this nutrient-dense stream enables the recovery of highly concentrated fertilizer products with comparatively low dilution and high agronomic value. Urine-derived fertilizers typically exhibit high mineral fertilizer equivalence (MFE), often exceeding 85%, and in some cases surpassing 100% for nitrified or acidified urine products due to improved nitrogen availability (Martin et al., 2021). Field and

FIGURE 10
Fertilizer production under Urine Diversion (UD) technology from scenarios 4–6.

greenhouse experiments further demonstrate that crops fertilized with urine-based products, whether stored, nitrified, or otherwise processed, achieve yields and nutrient uptake comparable to those obtained with conventional synthetic fertilizers (Viskari et al., 2018).

The increasing fertilizer outputs observed from S4 to S6 therefore represent a tangible opportunity to substitute a share of mineral fertilizers, whose production is energy-intensive and increasingly exposed to geopolitical and supply-chain risks related to natural gas and phosphate rock availability (Kok et al., 2018; Muellegger, 2005). This substitution potential is particularly relevant in the Swedish context, where agriculture relies almost entirely on imported mineral fertilizers and where national nitrogen and phosphorus flows remain strongly coupled to external inputs (Linderholm et al., 2012; Grados et al., 2025). Recent assessments further indicate that circular fertilizer products derived from UD can enhance regional nutrient self-sufficiency and reduce reliance on imported mineral fertilizers, particularly in Nordic and Baltic regions (Aliahmad et al., 2025; Lehtoranta et al., 2022).

When contextualized within Gotland's agricultural system, however, the absolute contribution of UD-derived fertilizer remains limited by population size. The island comprises approximately 86,000 ha of arable land. According to the simulations, fertilizer produced under Scenarios S4, S5, and S6 would correspond to approximately 0.03%, 0.05%, and 0.45% of Gotland's total fertilizer demand, respectively, when benchmarked against regional mineral fertilizer sales used as a proxy for demand (Statistics Sweden, 2025). When focusing specifically on barley production, the corresponding shares increased to approximately 0.2%, 0.38%, and 2.95%, reflecting the lower crop-specific nutrient demand relative to total agricultural production.

These findings reinforce the fundamentally population-bounded nature of urine diversion. While urine is highly concentrated in nutrients, the total recoverable mass is constrained by the number of contributing individuals rather than by the extent of agricultural land. Scenario-based extrapolations further illustrate this limitation and its implications for nutrient self-sufficiency. For example, the results indicate that full UD implementation (S6) based solely on

Visby's permanent population could yield approximately 50 ton yr⁻¹ of fertilizer. In contrast, sourcing urine from larger urban centers such as Stockholm, would substantially increase the substitution potential. Hypothetically, approximately 54% of Stockholm's population could meet 100% of the barley demand through UD systems. Even in this latter case, however, supplying fertilizer for all crops on Gotland would still require urine from the entire Stockholm population to cover only around 28% of total fertilizer demand (86,000 ha arable land). These comparisons underscore the scale mismatch between urban nutrient generation and agricultural nutrient demand and highlight the magnitude of current fertilizer dependency.

This dependency is further corroborated by nutrient-flow assessments for Gotland, which indicate that crop nitrogen demand exceeds the nitrogen content of locally available organic residues by a factor of approximately 2.4, necessitating continued reliance on imported mineral nitrogen. At the same time, the island exhibits a surplus of phosphorus in organic residues relative to crop demand, suggesting that improved redistribution, rather than additional imports, could reduce phosphorus dependency if logistical and regulatory barriers were addressed (Larsson et al., 2023).

Taken together, these results indicate that urine-derived fertilizers on Gotland should not be viewed as a complete replacement for mineral fertilizers, but rather as a strategic, high-value nutrient stream within an integrated nutrient management framework. Their greatest benefit lies in targeted application to crops located near urine collection and processing hubs, where transport distances, costs, and associated emissions can be minimized while nutrient-use efficiency is maximized. Beyond fertilizer substitution, UD delivers important co-benefits by reducing nitrogen and phosphorus loads entering centralized wastewater treatment plants and contributing to lower eutrophication pressure in the Baltic Sea. These outcomes align closely with the recommendations of the Baltic Stewardship Initiative (BSI, 2021), which emphasizes the need for combined technological solutions, precision fertilization, and valorization of urban biowaste streams to advance circular nutrient management and reduce environmental pressures on the Baltic Sea.

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that conventional centralized wastewater treatment systems in tourism-driven and climate-sensitive regions are highly vulnerable to short-term hydraulic overload, leading to recurrent seasonal exceedances of nitrogen and phosphorus discharge limits, increased marine eutrophication potential, and unstable environmental performance. The system dynamics modelling approach reveals that these impacts are driven primarily by transient peak loading conditions rather than average operational efficiency, highlighting a critical limitation of conventional assessment frameworks. The integration of urine diversion (UD) as a decentralized source-separation strategy significantly improves system performance by reducing peak nutrient loads, dampening seasonal variability, and enhancing overall operational stability. Even partial and seasonal implementation provides measurable benefits, while full-scale adoption achieves substantial reductions in nitrogen and phosphorus emissions (up to ~90% and ~80%, respectively), ensuring compliance with both current and forthcoming regulatory thresholds. In addition to mitigating eutrophication risks, UD contributes to reduced water abstraction, lower greenhouse gas emissions, and the recovery of valuable nutrients for fertilizer production, supporting circular economy objectives. Overall, the results indicate that coupling decentralized urine diversion with centralized treatment systems represents a robust and scalable strategy to enhance resilience, improve environmental performance, and transition wastewater management from reactive treatment toward proactive resource recovery in regions characterized by strong seasonal dynamics.

5 Future directions

Future research should build on the present work by advancing the integration of decentralized sanitation strategies within broader resource recovery and water management frameworks. Key priorities include:

- Incorporating socio-economic and governance factors to assess implementation feasibility and stakeholder acceptance.
- Expanding the modelling framework to additional decentralized technologies e.g., fertigation, microalgae biotechnology, feces composting and grey water reuse.
- Assessing the transferability of the approach across different regional and urban contexts.
- Integrating system dynamics with complementary tools such as Planetary Boundaries Life Cycle Assessment to support holistic decision-making.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/[Supplementary Material](#), further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Author contributions

EF: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing. PI: Data curation, Formal Analysis, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review and editing. JM: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal Analysis, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – original draft.

Funding

The author(s) declared that financial support was received for this work and/or its publication. This study was supported by funding from the European Union' Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme for the project "P2Green: Closing the gap between fork and farm for circular nutrient flows" (Grant number 101081883).

Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Generative AI statement

The author(s) declared that generative AI was used in the creation of this manuscript. Languages grammar verification.

Any alternative text (alt text) provided alongside figures in this article has been generated by Frontiers with the support of artificial intelligence and reasonable efforts have been made to ensure accuracy, including review by the authors wherever possible. If you identify any issues, please contact us.

Publisher's note

All claims expressed in this article are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent those of their affiliated organizations, or those of the publisher, the editors and the reviewers. Any product that may be evaluated in this article, or claim that may be made by its manufacturer, is not guaranteed or endorsed by the publisher.

Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fenvs.2026.1821368/full#supplementary-material>

References

- Aldaya, M. M., Chapagain, A. K., Hoekstra, A. Y., and Mekonnen, M. M. (2011). *The water footprint assessment manual: setting the global standard* (1st ed.). Routledge. doi:10.4324/9781849775526
- Aliahmad, A., Kanda, W., and McConville, J. (2023). Urine recycling - diffusion barriers and upscaling potential; case studies from Sweden and Switzerland. *J. Clean. Prod.* 414, 137583. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137583
- Aliahmad, A., Lima, P. de M., Kjerstadius, H., Simha, P., Vinnerås, B., and McConville, J. (2025). Consequential life cycle assessment of urban source-separating sanitation systems complementing centralized wastewater treatment in Lund, Sweden. *Water Res.* 268 (August 2024), 1–15. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2024.122741
- Almeida, A. T. (2013). *Processo de Decisão nas Organizações, 1 edn. Construindo modelos de decisão multicritério*. São Paulo: Editora Atlas S.A.
- Appiah-twum, H., Winckel, T. V., Santolin, J., Paepe, J., De Hellweg, S., Larsen, T. A., et al. (2025). Environmental impact of integrating decentralized urine treatment in the urban wastewater management system: a comparative life cycle assessment. *Water Res.* 282 (March), 123630. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2025.123630
- Bogdanova, M., Yotinov, I., and Topalova, Y. (2024). Comparison of the work of wastewater treatment plant "Ravda" in summer and winter influenced by the seasonal mass tourism industry and COVID-19. *Processes*, 12, 192. doi:10.3390/pr12010192
- Boiocchi, R., and Bertanza, G. (2022). Evaluating the potential impact of energy-efficient ammonia control on the carbon footprint of a full-scale wastewater treatment plant. *Water Sci. Technol.* 85 (5), 1673–1687. doi:10.2166/wst.2022.052
- Boiocchi, R., Matafome, B., Gargalo, C. L., Carvalho, A., and Sin, G. (2017). "Techno-economic analysis of resource recovery technologies for wastewater treatment plants," in *Computer aided chemical engineering (vol. 40)* (Elsevier Masson SAS). doi:10.1016/B978-0-444-63965-3.50326-3 (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- BSI (2021). *Ökad cirkularitet och minskad övergödning*. Baltic Stewardship Initiative. Available online at: <https://www.wwf.se/dokument/baltic-stewardship-initiative-okad-cirkularitet-och-minskad-overgodning/>. (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- Conroy, K. M., and Mancl, K. M. (2022). Understanding the adoption of urine-diverting dry toilets (UDDTs) in low-and lower-middle-income countries using the diffusion of innovation framework. *J. Water Sanitation Hyg. Dev.* 12 (12), 905–920. doi:10.2166/washdev.2022.154
- Dahlqvist, P., Sjöstrand, K., Lindhe, A., Rosén, L., Nisell, J., Hellstrand, E., et al. (2019). Potential benefits of managed aquifer recharge MAR on the Island of Gotland, Sweden. *Water* 11, 2164. doi:10.3390/w11102164
- Dutta, A., Sahoo, S., Mishra, R. R., Pradhan, B., Das, A., and Behera, B. C. (2019). A comparative study of citric acid production from different agro-industrial wastes by *Aspergillus niger* isolated from mangrove forest soil. 115–122. doi:10.22364/eeb.17.12
- Ecoinvent database (2024). *Treatment of wastewater, average, wastewater treatment, version*. Available online at: <https://ecoquery.ecoinvent.org/3.10/cutoff/dataset/25568/documentation>. (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- Ejhed, H., Fång, J., Hansen, K., Graae, L., Rahmberg, M., Magnér, J., et al. (2018). The effect of hydraulic retention time in onsite wastewater treatment and removal of pharmaceuticals, hormones and phenolic utility substances. *Sci. Total Environ.* 618, 250–261. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.11.011
- EU UWWTD (2024). *European union. Urban wastewater treatment directive: a guide for EU utilities*. Available online at: <https://www.cambi.com/blog/urban-wastewater-treatment-directive>. (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- Francisco, É. C., Ignácio, P. S. de A., Piolli, A. L., and Dal Poz, M. E. S. (2023). Food-energy-water (FEW) nexus: sustainable food production governance through system dynamics modelling journal of cleaner production. *J. Clean. Prod.* 386 (August 2022), 135825. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.135825
- Grados, D., Einarsson, R., Sanz-Cobena, Olesen, J. E., Borsting, C. F., and Abalos, D. (2025). Quantification and comparison of subnational and national agricultural nitrogen flows in Denmark and Sweden. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 20, 054041. doi:10.1088/1748-9326/adca4a
- Guest, J. S., Skerlos, S. J., Daigger, G. T., Corbett, J. R. E., and Love, N. G. (2010). The use of qualitative system dynamics to identify sustainability characteristics of decentralized wastewater management alternatives. *Water Sci. Technol.* 61 (6), 1637–1644. doi:10.2166/wst.2010.880
- Gustavsson, D. J. I., and Tumlin, S. (2013). Carbon footprints of Scandinavian wastewater treatment plants. *Water Sci. Technol.* 68 (4), 887–893. doi:10.2166/wst.2013.318
- Hållbarhetsredovisning (2023). *Destination Gotland*. Available online at: <https://www.destinationgotland.se/om-oss/hallbarhet-miljol>. (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- Harder, R., Wielemaker, R., Harder, R., Wielemaker, R., Larsen, T. A., and Zeeman, G. (2019). Technology recycling nutrients contained in human excreta to agriculture: pathways, processes, and products. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 49 (8), 695–743. doi:10.1080/10643389.2018.1558889
- HELCOM (2023a). *Baltic marine environment Protection commission – helsinki commission. Eutrophication thematic assessment 2016–2021. Baltic sea environment proceedings 192*. Available online at: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/HELCOM-Thematic-assessment-of-eutrophication-2016-2021.pdf>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- HELCOM (2023b). *State of the Baltic Sea. Third HELCOM holistic assessment 2016–2021. Baltic sea Environment proceedings n°194*. Available online at: <https://stateofthebalticsea.helcom.fi/> (Accessed October 16, 2025).
- Hilton, S. P., Keoleian, G. A., Daigger, G. T., Zhou, B., and Love, N. G. (2021). Life cycle assessment of urine diversion and conversion to fertilizer products at the city scale. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 55 (8), 593–603. doi:10.1021/acs.est.0c04195
- IPCC (2007). *Climate change 2007: synthesis report. Contribution of working groups I, II and III to the fourth assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*. (Accessed August 14, 2024)
- Jönsson, H., Baky, A., Jeppsson, U., Hellström, D., and Kärman, E. (2005). *Composition of urine, faeces, greywater and biowaste for utilization in the URWARE model. (urban water report; vol. 2005:6)*. Urban water, Chalmers University of Technology. Available online at: <http://www.iea.lth.se/publications/Reports/LTH-IEA-7222.pdf>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- Jordbruksverket (2022). *Agricultural statistics – nutrient balances and land use in Sweden*. Available online at: <https://jordbruksverket.se/statistik>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- Kok, D. J. D., Pande, S., van Lier, J. B., Ortigara, A. R. C., Savenije, H., and Uhlenbrook, S. (2018). Global phosphorus recovery from wastewater for agricultural reuse. *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* 22, 5781–5799. doi:10.5194/hess-22-5781-2018
- Kuokkanen, A., Blomberg, K., Mikola, A., and Heinonen, M. (2021). Unwanted mainstream nitrification-denitrification causing massive N₂O emissions in a continuous activated sludge process. *Water Sci. Technol.* 83 (9), 2207–2217. doi:10.2166/wst.2021.127
- Larsen, T. A., Udert, K. M., and Lienert, J. (2013). *Source separation and decentralization for wastewater management*. London: IWA Publishing. doi:10.3384/report.diva-194234
- Larsson, M., Tonderski, K., Metson, G., Quttineh, N. H., and Orsholm, J. (2023). *Towards a more circular biobased economy and nutrient use on Gotland: finding suitable locations for biogas plants. Biogas Solutions Research Center. 2023:2*. doi:10.3384/report.diva-194234
- Latif, A., Hassan, N., Ali, H., Niazi, M. B. K., Jahan, Z., Ghuman, I. L., et al. (2025). An overview of key industrial product citric acid production by *Aspergillus niger* and its application. *J. Industrial Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 52, kuaf007. doi:10.1093/jimb/kuaf007
- Lehtoranta, S., Laukka, V., Vidal, B., Heiderscheidt, E., Postila, H., Nilivaara, R., et al. (2022). Circular economy in wastewater management—the potential of source-separating sanitation in rural and peri-urban areas of Northern Finland and Sweden. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 10 (February), 1–18. doi:10.3389/fenvs.2022.804718
- Li, J., Li, X., Liu, H., Gao, L., Wang, W., Wang, Z., et al. (2023). Climate change impacts on wastewater infrastructure: a systematic review and typological adaptation strategy. *Water Res.* 242 (May), 120282. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2023.120282
- Linderholm, K., Mattsson, J. E., and Tillman, A. (2012). Phosphorus flows to and from Swedish agriculture and food chain. *AMBIO*, 41, 883–893. doi:10.1007/s13280-012-0294-1
- Macrotrends (2024). *Statistics Sweden*. Available online at: <https://www.macrotrends.net/global-metrics/countries/swe/sweden/population>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- Maktabifard, M., Zaborowska, E., and Makinia, J. (2019). Evaluating the effect of different operational strategies on the carbon footprint of wastewater treatment plants – case studies from northern Poland. *Water Sci. Technol.* 79 (11), 2211–2220. doi:10.2166/wst.2019.224
- Martin, T. M. P., Levvasseur, F., Dox, K., Tordera, L., Esculier, F., Smolders, E., et al. (2021). Physico-chemical characteristics and nitrogen use efficiency of nine human urine-based fertilizers in greenhouse conditions. *J. Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 21 (4), 2847–2856. doi:10.1007/s42729-021-00571-4
- Martin, T. M. P., Esculier, F., Levvasseur, F., and Houot, S. (2022). Human urine-based fertilizers: a review. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 52 (6), 890–936. doi:10.1080/10643389.2020.1838214
- Miljörapport (2017–2024). *Region gotland teknikförvaltningen VA-avdelningen avloppsheten*. Visby, Gotland/Sweden: Visby Avloppsreningsverk.
- Mkhize, N., Taylor, M., Udert, K. M., Gounden, T. G., and Buckley, C. A. (2017). Urine diversion dry toilets in eThekweni municipality, South Africa: acceptance, use and maintenance through users' eyes. *J. Water Sanitation Hyg. Dev.* 7 (1), 111–120. doi:10.2166/washdev.2017.079
- Mohammadifardi, H., Knight, M. A., and Unger, A. A. J. (2019). Sustainability assessment of asset management decisions for wastewater infrastructure systems—development of a system dynamic model. *Systems* 7 (2), 26. doi:10.3390/systems7020026
- Morera, S., Corominas, L., Poch, M., Aldaya, M. M., and Comas, J. (2016). Water footprint assessment in wastewater treatment plants. *J. Clean. Prod.* 112, 4741–4748. doi:10.1016/j.jclepro.2015.05.102
- Muellegger, E. (2005). Ecological Sanitation — a way to solve global sanitation problems? *Environ. Int.* 31, 433–444. doi:10.1016/j.envint.2004.08.006

- Mu'azu, N. D., Alagha, O., and Anil, I. (2020). Systematic modeling of municipal wastewater activated sludge process and treatment plant capacity analysis using GPS-X. *Sustain. Switz.* 12 (19), 1–26. doi:10.3390/su12198182
- Ni, X., Huang, X., Guo, R., Wang, J., Peng, K., Zhang, W., et al. (2023). Water–energy–carbon synergies and trade-offs: a daily nexus analysis for wastewater treatment plants. *Resour. Conservation Recycl.* 188, 106712. doi:10.1016/j.resconrec.2022.106712
- P2Green project (2024). *P2Green project*. Available online at: <https://p2green.eu/about/>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- Perry, W. B., Ahmadian, R., Munday, M., Jones, O., Ormerod, S. J., and Durance, I. (2024). Addressing the challenges of combined sewer overflows. *Environ. Pollut.* 343 (October 2023), 123225. doi:10.1016/j.envpol.2023.123225
- Preisner, M., Smol, M., and Szoldrowska, D. (2021). Trends, insights and effects of the Urban Wastewater Treatment Directive (91/271/EEC) implementation in the light of the Polish coastal zone eutrophication. *Environ. Manag.* 67 (2), 342–354. doi:10.1007/s00267-020-01401-6
- Prouty, C., Mohebbi, S., and Zhang, Q. (2020). Extreme weather events and wastewater infrastructure: a system dynamics model of a multi-level, socio-technical transition. *Sci. Total Environ.* 714, 136685. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.136685
- Räike, A., Taskinen, A., and Knuutila, S. (2020). Nutrient export from Finnish rivers into the Baltic Sea has not decreased despite water protection measures. *Ambio* 49 (2), 460–474. doi:10.1007/s13280-019-01217-7
- Rauch, W., Brockmann, D., Peters, I., Larsen, T. A., and Gujer, W. (2003). Combining urine separation with waste design: an analysis using a stochastic model for urine production. *Water Res.* 37, 681–689. doi:10.1016/s0043-1354(02)00364-0
- Raven, R., Bosch, S. V. d., and Weterings, R. (2010). Transitions and strategic niche management: towards a competence kit for practitioners transitions and strategic niche management: towards a competence kit for practitioners. *Internat. J. Technol. Manag.* 51, 57. doi:10.1504/IJTM.2010.033128
- Region Gotland (2023). *Region Gotland*. Available online at: <https://www.gotland.se/visbyreningsverk> (Accessed August 14, 2024).
- Reppas-Chrysovitinos, E., Svanström, M., and Peters, G. (2024). Estimating fossil carbon contributions from chemicals and microplastics in Sweden's urban wastewater systems: a model-based approach. *Heliyon* 10 (18), e37665. doi:10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e37665
- Richardson, K., Steffen, W., Lucht, W., Bendtsen, J., Cornell, S. E., Donges, J. F., et al. (2023). Earth beyond six of nine planetary boundaries. *Sci. Adv.* 9, 1–16. doi:10.1126/sciadv.adh2458
- Rose, C., Parker, A., Jefferson, B., Cartmell, E., Parker, A., Jefferson, B., et al. (2015). The characterization of feces and urine: a review of the literature to inform advanced treatment technology the characterization of feces and urine. *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 45, 1827–1879. doi:10.1080/10643389.2014.1000761
- Rumeau, M., Marsden, C., Ait-mouheb, N., Crevoisier, D., Rumeau, M., Marsden, C., et al. (2023). Fate of nitrogen and phosphorus from source-separated human urine in a calcareous soil. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* 30, 65440–65454. doi:10.1007/s11356-023-26895-5
- Saikia, S. D., Ryan, P., Nuyts, S., Nolan, P., and Clifford, E. (2024). Impacts of projected future changes in precipitation on wastewater treatment plant influent volumes connected by combined sewer collection systems. *Clim. Serv.* 35, 100511. doi:10.1016/j.cliser.2024.100511
- Saliu, T. D., Oladoja, N. A., and Sauvé, S. (2024). Eco-friendly and sustainability assessment of technologies for nutrient recovery from human urine — a review. *Front. Sustain.* 4, 1–20. doi:10.3389/frsus.2023.1338380
- Sanitation360 (2025). Available online at: <https://sanitation360.se/>. (Accessed October 16, 2025)
- Shao, L., and Chen, G. Q. (2013). Water footprint assessment for wastewater treatment: method, indicator, and application. *Environ. Sci. Technol.* 47, 7787–7794. doi:10.1021/es4021013t
- Song, C., Zhu, J., Willis, J. L., Moore, D. P., Zondlo, M. A., and Ren, Z. J. (2024). Oversimplification and misestimation of nitrous oxide emissions from wastewater treatment plants. *Nat. Sustain.* 7 (October), 1348–1358. doi:10.1038/s41893-024-01420-9
- Statistics Sweden (SCB) (2023a). Land use statistics. Available online at: <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/environment/land-use/>. (Accessed January 22, 2026)
- Statistics Sweden (SCB) (2023b). Industrial activity statistics. Available online at: <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/business-activities/>. (Accessed January 22, 2026)
- Statistics Sweden (2025). Available online at: <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/environment/land-use/>. (Accessed January 22, 2026)
- STELLA (2023). *ISEE systems (version 3.7.3)*. Lebanon, NH: ISEE systems. Available online at: <https://77www.iseesystems.com>
- Swedavia Statistica (2021–2024). *Swedavia airports. Trafikstatistik på swedavia flygplatser*. Available online at: <https://www.swedavia.se/om-swedavia/statistik/> (Accessed August 14, 2024).
- Todt, D., Bisschops, I., Chatzopoulos, P., and Van Eekert, M. H. A. (2021). Practical performance and user experience of novel DUAL-flush vacuum toilets. *WaterSwitzerl.* 13 (16), 1–14. doi:10.3390/w13162228
- Ukkonen, P., and Mikola, A. (2024). Novel dissolved oxygen distribution model of a full-scale aeration tank for a municipal wastewater treatment plant in a cold climate region. 15(11), 5698–5713. doi:10.2166/wcc.2024.667
- Varol, S., Alver, A., and Altaş, L. (2024). The water footprint assessment for advanced biological wastewater treatment plant. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* 21 (2), 2035–2048. doi:10.1007/s13762-023-05242-8
- Vatten, S. (2023). *Investeringsbehov och framtida kostnader för kommunalt vatten och avlopp - en analys av investeringsbehov 2022-2040. Rapport R2023-02*. Available online at: https://vattenbokhandeln.svensktvatten.se/wp-content/uploads/2023/05/SvensktVatten-Investeringsrapport_2023.pdf (Accessed October 16, 2025).
- Vinnerås, B., Palmquist, H., Balmer, P., and Jönsson, H. (2006). The characteristics of household wastewater and biodegradable solid waste - a proposal for new Swedish design values. *Urban Water J.- Urban Water* 3, 3–11. doi:10.1080/15730620600578629
- Viskari, E. L., Grobler, G., Karimäki, K., Gorbatova, A., Vilpas, R., and Lehtoranta, S. (2018). Nitrogen recovery with source separation of human urine—preliminary results of its fertiliser potential and use in agriculture. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 2 (June), 1–14. doi:10.3389/fsufs.2018.00032
- Vos, R., Glauber, J., Hebebrand, C., and Rice, B. (2025). Global shocks to fertilizer markets: impacts on prices, demand and farm profitability. *Food Policy* 133 (November 2024), 102790. doi:10.1016/j.foodpol.2024.102790
- Wang, H., Zhang, X., Li, L., Lin, Z., and Tian, Y. (2025). Carbon emission characteristics and low-carbon operation evaluation of some wastewater treatment plants in east China: an empirical study based on actual production data. *Appl. Sci. Switz.* 15 (12), 1–24. doi:10.3390/app15126716
- West, T. P. (2023). Citric acid production by *Aspergillus niger* using solid-state fermentation of agricultural processing coproducts. *Appl. Biosci.* 2 (1), 1–13. doi:10.3390/applbiosci2010001
- Xiang, C., Koskue, V., Duan, H., Gao, L., Kyong, H., Martin, G. J. O., et al. (2024). Science of the total environment impact of nutrient deficiency on biological sewage treatment - perspectives towards urine source segregation. *Sci. Total Environ.* 946 (April), 174174. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.174174
- Zhang, C., Guisasaola, A., and Baeza, J. A. (2022). A review on the integration of mainstream P-recovery strategies with enhanced biological phosphorus removal. *Water Res.* 212, 118102. doi:10.1016/j.watres.2022.118102